

An EEG data fusion approach based on deep learning for brain motor image classification

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Abstract This paper explores Deep Learning (DL) method to classify Motor Imagery (MI) based on electroencephalogram (EEG) brainwaves data using the two feature extractors Independent Component Analysis (ICA) and Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT). The contribution of this paper is in the processing phase, more precisely in the intermediate level by applying the fuzzy logic fusion method to combine the information from these two methods. The objective is to predict the MI from EEG signals after applying several algorithms and techniques.

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) was applied in 2a dataset from the brain computer interface (BCI) Competition IV during the classification phase, whence comparison between CNN and different classifiers is made, while considering the comparison between the fusion method and each feature extractor separately.

The results proved that CNN is the best classifier for each of the classes and for the overall data set. Thus they showed that the adapted fusion method performed well, hence it improved the sense of class prediction by recording the best classification rates.

Key words Brain Computer Interface, Motor Imagery, Electroencephalography, Classification, Deep Learning

1 Introduction

Over the past decades, thanks to a wide variety of emerging technologies and computing paradigms, computing capacity has seen substantial increases. As a result, many problems can now be solved, and many successful research methods have emerged in other fields.

Nowadays, BCI is one of the most important areas of neuroscience in which the human brain controls the functioning of the machine, hence brain activity can be recorded and analyzed in several ways using BCIs. Motor imaging is a mental technique commonly used to change brain oscillations and run a BCI [1].

BCI design is a difficult and complex task, it consists of two phases, the first is offline for system training and the second is online for recognizing mental states and translating them into commands for a computer. This process begins when the user engages in a cognitive task while receiving possible stimuli, which the subject is found in various real situations to control his emotions by reacting to different stimuli, either visual (images, photos), audio (sounds, music) or audio-visual (video clips, films).

EEG classification of motor imagery is a crucial task in the BCI system, the overall objective of which is to increase user performance.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In the next section, we present the related works that have studied the different methods and algorithms for classification of motor images in brain computer interfaces. In section III, we define our working approach. The results obtained from this study are discussed in section IV . Finally, a brief conclusion that sums up the work and future work are presented in last section.

2 RELATED WORKS

In the literature, many researches were proposed for the MI classification in BCI. In this section, we present some related works.

Zhang and Eskandarian [2] applied time series data extraction and band pass filter for preprocessing brain EEG signal data. Then they used common spatial pattern (CSP) to extract eight characteristics from the four classes. And for the classification, the three classifiers linear discriminant analysis (LDA), Naive bayes (NB), support vector machine (SVM) were applied to finish with a comparison.

Tan et al. [3] proposed an algorithm based on the merging method on the BCI competition III IVa dataset, they used CSP and WT for feature extraction, and a Bayesian decision-based merge algorithm to merge the results of two classifiers under different aspects which are SVM and LDA.

Ortiz-Echeverri et al. [4] proposed a combination of Blind source separation (BSS) and wavelet transform (WT) to extract features based on the CNN approach for classification.

Djemaal et al. [5] used Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) and Autoregressive modeling (AR) for the feature extraction phase after applying the elliptic band-pass filter for artefact removing. This experiment contains two datasets. For the classification, multi-LDA and multi-SVM classifiers were used.

Gonzalez et al, [6] used CSP as a feature extraction method added to the Root Mean Square statistical method (RMS). The classification algorithms used were, KNN,SVM, Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) and Dendrite Morphological Neural Networks (DMNN).

As a discussion, various works used machine learning (ML) algorithms for the MI study such as SVM, DT, K-NN and CNN. For feature extraction, many methods have been used such as CSP, FFT, AR, ICA and WT.

Features extracted in the time - frequency domain are one of the best for recognizing mental tasks based on EEG signals [7]. Hence characteristics based on wavelet methods

are best for EEG-type signals. These methods are suitable for non-stationary signals and they are able to analyze the signal in both time and frequency domains. Thus ICA is one of the best spatial methods thanks to its simplicity and robustness, it is efficient in terms of computation and it has a high performance for a large data size [8].

In this section, we summarized the related works which focused on BCI MI classification using artificial intelligence (AI) techniques through various methods such as ML. We explore our proposed approach in the next section.

3 PROPOSED APPROACH

3.1 Data Acquisition

After the phase of the acquisition of data from sensors, a visual inspection of all data sets was performed by an expert during the motion imaging period by marking the assays that contain artifacts. A regression-based EOG reduction method is applied due to its simplicity and robustness.

In this experiment, the BCI Competition IV-2a dataset was used, from which EEG signals were recorded using twenty-two Ag / AgCl electrodes from nine healthy subjects (three women and six men with a mean age of 23.8 years and a standard deviation of 2.5 years). The signals of the 22 EEG channels and 3 EOG channels were sampled at 250 Hz and bandwidth filtered between 0.5 Hz and 100 Hz, from where EOG were filtered with an additional 50 Hz notch filter which was activated to remove the noise [9].

Four different motor imagery classes were included in this database, namely the imaginary movement of the left hand, right hand, both feet and tongue.

Each subject records two sessions on different days, one for training and the other for evaluation. Each is made up of 6 attempts separated by pauses of 1.25 s. Each trial consists of 12 trials for each of the four classes, for a total of 288 trials per session. At the start of each test, a fixing cross appeared on the black screen accompanied by a short warning tone. At $t = 2$ s, an arrow-shaped signal pointing in the four directions corresponding to the four classes appeared for 1.25 s. This prompted subjects to perform the desired motor imaging task until the fixation cross disappeared from the screen at $t = 6$ s. A short pause followed lasting at least 1.5 s, where the screen was black again.

3.2 Feature Extraction

One of the most difficult problems in the design of BCI is the extraction of the relevant EEG characteristics, who tries to find an optimal subset of relevant features so that the overall classification accuracy is increased while the data size is reduced and the recognition performance is improved.

For this step, we chose to use the two methods DWT and ICA for various reasons. First, DWT is a spectral estimation technique that extracts frequency content using a

time window of variable duration [10]. This technique plays an important role in the field of neuroscience recognition, where it attempts to transfer the time varying signal, which includes many data points, into a few small parameters represented as an infinite series that represent the signal. These parameters are called wavelets which are mathematical functions to provide a flexible way of time-frequency representation of a signal. Thus, the use of time-frequency domain methods, is the most suitable way to extract characteristics from the raw data of non-stationary signals, in our case, hence the WT is intended to solve the problems of EEG signals [11].

For ICA, as the name suggests, it is characterized by its ability to identify statistically independent components based on the distribution of input data, it is computationally efficient [12], extracts frequency content using a time window of variable duration and offers high performance for large data. So this method is efficient when the recorded signal is multi channel, and this is our case.

3.3 Fuzzy logic

Data fusion allows you to combine data of all types and from any source to get better, actionable insights faster. The combination oftentimes is due to two sets of data, from which it usually highlights useful information that would not have been discovered without applying data fusion, hence this information offers a new perspective that can lead to decisions more enlightened.

For the first phase, fuzzification is a delicate phase which consists of transforming the real values of a variable into fuzzy variables, from where it is necessary to fuzzify the inputs and outputs of the fuzzy process.

For each variable, we must first define the universe of discourse which is a range of possible variations of the input considered, a partition into fuzzy classes of this universe called fuzzy variables and the membership functions of each of these classes. For this step, we used the Mamdani method which has for principle, the more the condition on the inputs is true, the more the recommended action for the outputs must be respected.

$$Mam : \mu'_{conclusion}(y) = MIN_y(\mu_{premise}(x_0), \mu_{conclusion}(y)) \quad (1)$$

After fuzzifying the input and output variables, you need to establish the rules linking the inputs to the outputs.

Among the most popular fuzzy set operators are the Zadeh operators **T-norm** **T-conorme** and **negation** which can be used to define the fuzzy intersection [13], where T is the abbreviation of "triangular". We used the first which is dedicated for the conjunction, its truth value is the minimum between the two premise truth values.

$$\mu_{A \cap B}(x) = min(\mu_A(x), \mu_B(x)) \quad (2)$$

For the defuzzification step, this is the process of converting a membership function into a physical quantity. This membership function is the set of values obtained by combining

the rules applied to the fuzzy intervals of the output variable. We opted for the center of gravity (COG) method which is the abscissa of the center of gravity of the output curve. This method is the most used since it takes into account the influence of all the values proposed by the fuzzy solution.

3.4 Classification

After applying the two feature extractors ICA and DWT on the BCI Competition IV dataset 2a, we applied the merging method of these methods which is fuzzy logic to ensure better performance. Then we will try to classify this data using the CNN classifier. Classification is a process of predicting classes (types of mental state identified) from an extracted set of characteristics. For this part, we have chosen to use a CNN deep learning classification algorithm which is an architecture based on a kind of specialized linear operation known as convolution [14]. This type of networks is suitable for processing different types of signals such as audio, video, images and medical signals and especially EEG. This architecture has achieved remarkable success in BCIs, therefore, several works based on EEG analysis, have used CNN as a classifier.

In our work, first, the merged EEG signal from ICA and DWT is converted to a matrix representation, then this data is fed in as the input of the model, from where we used a CNN with three hidden layers, the first is that of convolution of size 3 x 3 which has 256 characteristics, the result of convolution is called "Feature maps", and each value of this map is transmitted thereafter to the next layer. The second is the pooling layer of size 2 x 2 using max pooling, which tries to choose the maximum elements of each characteristic card, it has 128 characteristics. Then we used the softmax function to finish with the prediction of the four classes, right hand, left hand, tongue and both feet.

4 Classification performance

In our study, besides the CNN application, we applied four models to classify the BCI competition IV - 2a dataset, namely, SVM with a linear kernel, DT hence the maximum number of divisions equal to 100, K-NN with a number of neighbors K equal to 1 and a euclidean distance and LDA. In machine learning, each model has a classification rate, which must be calculated to properly evaluate classification algorithms. Each has two sets of data, one for learning, and the other for testing which is the basis for verifying predictions. For each class, we calculated the classification rate before and after the merge method of the two feature extractors ICA and DWT, using the five classifiers; CNN, SVM, K-NN, DT and LDA.

After applying ICA and DWT, we applied fuzzy logic at the mid-level to significantly improve classification rates. So we compared the classification rates before and after using the fusion method. We thus calculated the classification rate for the entire 2a data set. CNN performed better than other classifiers and especially after applying fuzzy logic.

Generally motor images of the upper limbs (right hand and left hand) are best detected for all approaches at a rate of almost 98 %.

Table 1. BCI competition dataset 2a classification rate table

	ICA	DWT	Fusion
CNN	96.20 %	97.11 %	97.56 %
SVM	90.62 %	91.89 %	92.72 %
K-NN	86.71 %	90.21 %	90.54 %
DT	81.59 %	85.84 %	86.25 %
LDA	91.07 %	93.16 %	93.79 %

5 Conclusion and perspectives

All the works and applications discussed in this paper make it much easier to learn more about the variety and significance of using ML algorithms for the classification of BCI MI. CNN, SVM, K-NN and DT are the most used techniques and often have the best accuracies. This paper proposes and tests the application of two feature extractors ICA and DWT and then merge them using the fuzzy logic method to improve the performance of decision making and recognition, hence, we concluded that the merging method at the intermediate level is efficient, feasible and gives precise results, and it depends on the methods used for the fuzzy intersection. Then CNN was applied as classification method. For all predicted classes and even for the whole dataset, using fuzzy logic with the CNN application gave the best results : (for the right hand : 97.86 %, for the left hand : 98.14 %, for the two feet : 96.89 %, for the tongue : 97.35 % and for the whole dataset : 97.56 %). Although our approach recorded high rates, it is not always efficient, hence, the overall classification using fuzzy logic may be affected by the low accuracy of some classifiers that have low rates. So in this case, the classification without using the fusion performs better. The ideal method of feature extraction, which is at the same time robust, invariant over time and universal does not exist and remains to be found, from which many works are being carried out and will be carried out based on BCIs for remedy imperfections.

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